

ULTRASONIC MOTION ESTIMATION TECHNIQUES FOR MUSICAL APPLICATIONS

Ludvig ELBLAUS (ludvig.elblaus@kmh.se)¹, Daniele POZZI (daniele.pozzi@student.kug.ac.at)², and Gerhard ECKEL (eckel@iem.at)³

¹Royal College of Music, Stockholm, Sweden

²University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, Graz, Austria

³Institute for Electronic Music and Acoustics, Graz, Austria

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a method for motion estimation tailored to musical applications, based on ultrasonic sensing and affordable, off-the-shelf hardware. The system operates effectively across a wide range of spatial scales — from sub-centimetre precision in compact setups to room-scale tracking — offering millimetre-level resolution under favourable conditions. Three case studies demonstrate the approach’s flexibility and potential for diverse musical contexts. Technical aspects of the core system are detailed, and the paper encourages further exploration of ultrasonic motion tracking in musical settings, particularly in larger spatial environments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Physical interaction has always been a central concern for the development of digital musical instruments, as evident in the NIME and SMC communities. While the majority of efforts are spent on designing physical artefacts, a substantial part of the community projects involve the detection, analysis, and interaction with bodily movement that is not sensed through physical touch. This can include putting sensors on the body to detect movement, or using camera-based systems to register and act on movement. The camera-based solutions tend to fall into two categories, either performing image analysis in the visible light spectrum or using specialised motion capture rigs in the infra-red spectrum.

The authors have substantial experience with camera-based motion capture systems [1–5] and while they certainly offer particular characteristics in terms of precision and mapping of three-dimensional models onto a moving body, the work presented in this paper represents a departure from this kind of high-fidelity motion capture. Instead, we present a low-cost solution that scales all the way up to room-scale motion estimation using ultrasound. Ultrasound systems are not completely new to the field of SMC, but they tend to be used exclusively in smaller scale setups.

In this paper, three practical applications of ultrasound

motion estimation systems for real-time musical production are presented. The examples are a selection of pieces from the authors’ own artistic practices and are presented in order of increasing scale of the physical volume sensed with ultrasound. These approaches share a common technical foundation but offer some variety in their approach to musical applications of ultrasound sensing and subsequent results.

The paper is structured as follows: First, in Section 2, a general overview of ultrasonic motion capture is given, followed by some examples of specific musical applications. Then, in Section 3, the proposed concept of room-scale ultrasonic motion estimation is presented. This is followed by Section 4, offering a technical presentation of the underlying hardware and software used in all three case studies, that are then presented in Section 5. The case studies are compared and discussed in Section 6 which is followed by a concluding summary of the paper.

2. BACKGROUND

Ultrasonic technology has found an evolving role in experimental music and sound art, with applications ranging from highly directional sound reproduction to movement-responsive compositions. One of the most widely known uses of ultrasonics in music is the parametric loudspeaker, such as the Audio Spotlight, which achieves precise sound directionality through amplitude modulation [6–8]. However, composers and musicians also experimented with this technology, exploring its potential for interactive and immersive musical experiences. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, David Tudor pioneered the integration of ultrasonic systems into live performances and installations. In collaboration with visual artist Jacqueline Matisse Monnier, he created works like *Lines and Reflections* (1988) and *Virtual Focus* (1990). Tudor’s setups used ultrasonic sensors and radar to track the movements of Matisse’s suspended sculptures, translating their dynamic shifts into control signals for electronic sound circuits. This approach was further explored in Merce Cunningham’s dance piece *Polarity* (1990), where Tudor directed ultrasonic sonar and radar at the dancers. The inaudible waves reflected by the dancers’ movements modulated audible sound, adding a layer of sonic responsiveness to the choreography [9].

In the 2000s, ultrasonic experimentation has continued in the work of Overholt, who developed an ultrasound-

Copyright: © 2025. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

augmented violin, expanding the instrument’s expressive capabilities [10]. Similarly, Ciglar designed a musical interface with an array of ultrasonic transducers, enabling performers to manipulate audio in mid-air through haptic gestures [11]. Raes contributed a system that detects a performer’s bodily movements via continuous ultrasonic reflections, furthering the exploration of body-as-instrument dynamics [12].

Other artists have embraced the spatial and perceptual effects of ultrasonic sound. In *Listening to the Air*, Kuivila explored how ultrasonic emissions interact with the surrounding environment [13]. Robson’s installation *Being With The Waves* featured a multi-channel ultrasonic composition emitted from an array of tweeters. Listeners wearing specially equipped headphones could experience ultrasonic phenomena captured by microphones embedded in the ear cups, where the sound was shifted into the audible range. This setup produced dramatic effects, such as exaggerated Doppler shifts, making the music bend and morph with the listener’s movements through space [14].

Despite the diversity of approaches, these applications remain relatively isolated examples, focusing on small scale detection, indicating that the use of ultrasonic technology for movement detection in musical contexts is an area with significant potential for further exploration and development, especially when expanding to room-scale setups.

3. ULTRASONIC MOTION ESTIMATION

The approach proposed in this paper allows for motion estimation using low-cost off-the-shelf components that allow to capture volumes that range from very small to as large as room-scale volumes. This is achieved by working towards total motion level estimation rather than motion tracking of absolute position. However, for musical applications, knowing when and how much motion has happened is often enough to make informed real-time decisions.

We want to highlight the following benefits of our approach to be described in technical detail in the next section:

- Low cost compared to camera based solutions, very low cost compared to infrared motion capture systems.
- Sub centimeter resolution in most conditions and millimeter precision in certain conditions.
- Negligible processing time, scaling with processing power, easily well under 10 milliseconds.
- Insensitive to sounds in the audible range, changes in light conditions, or other environmental factors.
- Virtually no need for calibration or tuning.

Leveraging our previous experience with different high-fidelity motion capture technologies [1–3] we firmly believe that the trade-off between complete motion capture and all the complications and expense that come with it

compared to motion estimation and the low-cost plug-and-play character of the systems used in the case studies is one that is very worthwhile to explore. It is certainly not a suitable solution for every situation, but we argue that it is an under explored approach, especially given its availability and low complexity.

4. TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The motion detection system described leverages commonly available and cost-effective ultrasound transducers, paired with low-cost USB audio interfaces capable of operating at 96 kHz. This configuration allows for effective system operation at an ultrasound frequency of 40 kHz. The setup includes various configurations of transmitters that emit a constant frequency ultrasound throughout the space. Receivers then pick up the ultrasound signals that have been reflected and modulated by moving objects within the space.

Importantly, the ultrasound signals captured by the receivers are modulated due to changing interferences caused by the dynamic occlusion of different reflection paths. This modulation occurs as objects move within the space, altering the paths and characteristics of the reflected ultrasound waves. The process of demodulating these signals, primarily through extracting their amplitude envelope, enables the estimation of overall motion within the observed volume. This includes not only moving objects but also variations in air circulation.

The necessary signal processing for demodulating and analysing these signals can be effectively implemented using popular open-source computer music tools such as SuperCollider or PureData. These tools provide the needed capabilities to handle the signal processing tasks involved in this system without incurring in high costs.

4.1 Hardware

In our setup, we use Hailege TCT40-16 ultrasonic transmitters and receivers, each with a 16 mm diameter and operating at a frequency of 40 kHz. The transmitters are capable of being driven by signals of up to 60V.

For our purposes, they were directly connected to the line or headphone outputs of an audio interface, such as the Behringer UMC1820. To maximise output, we employed the stereo headphone outputs, driving them with two 40 kHz sine waves in counter phase. This setup allowed us to bridge the transmitters across the left and right channels.

In certain cases, to enhance the signal strength and broaden the coverage area, we configured multiple transmitters into arrays (see Fig.6). For the detection of ultrasonic signals, we primarily used the ultrasonic receivers; however, in some cases, we also employed omnidirectional microphones capable of capturing frequencies up to 40 kHz, like the Sennheiser MKE2 lavalier microphone. This dual approach allowed us to adapt our detection strategy based on the specific requirements and constraints of different applications, ensuring flexibility and effectiveness in our system setup.

```

var computeRMS, computeSlopeRMS;
var ultra, ultraRMS, slope;
var motion, sonification, bw;

bw = 500;

// FUNCTIONS
computeRMS = { |sig, bw|
  sig = sig.squared();
  4.do({ sig = BLowPass.ar(sig, bw, 2) });
  sig.sqrt();
};

computeSlopeRMS = { |sig, bw, threshold, range|
  sig = computeRMS.(sig, bw);
  sig = sig.ampdb();
  sig = sig - threshold;
  sig = sig.max(0) / range;
  sig.min(1)
};

// TRANSMIT
Out.ar(0, SinOsc.ar(40000));

// RECEIVE, ANALYZE, SONIFY
ultra = SoundIn.ar(0);
4.do({ ultra = BHiPass.ar(ultra, 30000, 2) });
ultraRMS = computeRMS.(ultra, bw);
slope = Slope.ar(ultraRMS);
motion = computeSlopeRMS.(slope, 20, -40, 70);
sonification = slope * SinOsc.ar(bw);
sonification = BBandStop.ar(sonification, bw, 0.5);

[sonification, motion]

```

Figure 1. SuperCollider code that transmits the 40kHz sine wave and receives the incoming audio, isolates the ultrasound part, analyses and sonifies it. The final line returns the two results, the sonification in `sonification` and the analysed motion estimation in `motion`.

4.2 Software

The signal processing software designed for our motion detection system functions at a sampling rate of 96 kHz, a necessity to effectively manage the 40 kHz signals utilised by the transmitters and receivers. The software generates a consistent 40 kHz sine wave that is sent to the ultrasound transmitters, and it also processes the signals received from the receivers or microphone. From the incoming signal, we derive the magnitude of amplitude changes, which is directly proportional to the amount of movement within the detection volume.

To achieve this, we first extract the amplitude envelope of the signal. This is done by squaring the signal, which rectifies it, followed by applying a low pass filter to smooth out fast fluctuations. The square root of this smoothed, unipolar signal is then calculated to recover the envelope, a technique known as envelope following. To assess the extent of change, we then differentiate this envelope, resulting in a bipolar signal. This differentiated signal undergoes a second round of envelope extraction, essentially capturing the magnitude of dynamic changes once more. This entire sequence, which we term "envelope dynamics analysis," effectively highlights dynamic changes in the signal's characteristics.

Figure 2. *Autotropo n.4* performance setup. The metal plate is equipped with a vibration transducer, a contact microphone and an ultrasound transmitter-receiver pair.

5. CASE STUDIES

In this section we will present three case studies of practical applications of ultrasonic motion estimation taken from the authors' own artistic production. The pieces are *Autotropo n.4* by Daniele Pozzi (2024), *Speculator* by Gerhard Eckel (2024) and *The Season of Sound* by Gerhard Eckel & Ludvig Elblaus (2025).

5.1 Autotropo n.4

Autotropo n.4 is part of a series of improvisations exploring various forms of electro-acoustic and electro-mechanical coupling between a digital feedback system and selected physical objects. In *Autotropo n.4*, the system is coupled to a 45x45 centimetre iron plate, of the type normally used for enamelling, via a vibration transducer for sound excitation and a contact microphone for sound detection (Fig. 2). The signal from the contact microphone is the input to the digital feedback system, whose output is in turn fed to the transducer, causing the plate to vibrate. The metal plate thus acts as a physical filter that modifies the signal processing chain, with a sonic response that depends on the dimensions of the plate and the specific positions at which the transducers are mounted. A miniature hand-held microphone also inputs to the systems, allowing to detect vibrations at different points of the plate and enabling a direct interaction with its modes of resonance.

A motion detection system is installed right above the surface of the plate (Fig. 3), consisting of a pair of ultrasonic emitter-receivers mounted at opposite sides, with the two transducers facing each other. This allows to detect additional information about the performer's hand movements, as well as the swinging of the plate itself, which is suspended through a metal hook attached to a microphone stand. The improvisation alternates between sections in which the performer's hands touch the metal plate, or are very close to it, and other moments in which the plate is left untouched while the performer stands still in its vicinity. The ultrasound signal is filtered differently in the two sections: when the performer is actively manipulating the plate, the motion detection system is used as a trigger, de-

Figure 3. Ultrasonic transducers are mounted by screwing a small metal hook into the center hole of an electric connection terminal.

etecting only sudden or large hand movements. This is done by averaging the magnitude of amplitude changes over two different time windows and comparing their average values. If the value of the shorter window is significantly larger than the longer one, a sudden change is detected and the digital feedback system is directed to change its configuration. In the sections where the performer is not interacting with the plate, the ultrasonic signal is simply low-passed and fed directly into the digital feedback system, acting as a simple modulator.

This use of motion detection is intended to enhance improvisation by incorporating ancillary aspects of performance into the piece. In particular, the threshold of the trigger mechanism described above is set at a level that detects mostly intentional movements, but can also be triggered by non-intentional gestures. This adds a layer of unpredictability to the improvisation, which is nevertheless tied to the unfolding of the performance itself.

Autotropo n.4 was premiered at the Austrian Composers Week 2024, Konzerthaus Klagenfurt, Austria, in October 2024. An audio recording of the performance is available at <https://www.danielepozzi.com/tropi/>

5.2 Speculator

Speculator [15] is a composition for an electro-acoustically enhanced double bass that utilises two vibration transducers for sound excitation. One transducer is mounted on the top plate above the bass bar, while the other, a handheld unit with a felt-covered staple, is used to inject vibrations at various points on the instrument. Each string of the double bass is equipped with an electromagnetic pickup, allowing to form feedback loops with the transducers through signal processing algorithms specifically crafted for this piece.

Integrated into the double bass is a motion detection system, as described in the document, which uses the performer's hand and body movements to modulate the signal processing. An ultrasound emitter is positioned on the bridge, directing signals towards the fingerboard, while a receiver is placed just below and at the top of the fingerboard. This setup not only focuses on detecting movement

Figure 4. *Speculator* performance setup. The double bass is equipped with one vibration transducer, four electromagnetic pickups and an ultrasound transmitter-receiver pair.

on the top plate of the instrument, e.g. when operating the handheld transducer there, but also captures surrounding movements. Thus, all performance-related and incidental movements of the player can be made to contribute to modulating the sound, enriching the musical expression.

One of the artistic intentions of *Speculator* was to intertwine the various spaces that make up the performance setup, adding layers of complexity and interaction. These include the local mechano-acoustic space of the instrument itself, the acoustic environment of the performance venue, the algorithmic space defined by the signal processing, and the ultrasonic space that detects movement, including the vibrations of the bass and even the breath of the performer. This multidimensional approach aims to create a rich, immersive experience that blurs the lines between these different spaces, enhancing both the performative and auditory experience.

A video recording of the performance is available at <https://speculativesoundsynthesis.iem.sh/symposium/docs/proceedings/eckel/>.

5.3 The Season of Sound

Der Betrieb in Vienna, Austria, is a venue owned and operated by *Kunstverein Archipelago*, a dance company that choreographs and performs two pieces per year at *Der Betrieb*, divided into two seasons of about six weeks each. In the spring of 2025, *utrumque* (Eckel and Elblaus), collaborated with Archipelago in developing and performing the *Season of Sound*, a dance performance with a focus on sound, sounding, listening and site-specific installation.

Figure 5. Der Betrieb.

The full description of this work is beyond the scope of this paper, but a short general summary will be provided here for context, before the specific use of ultrasonic motion estimation is described in more detail.

For the Season of Sound, *Der Betrieb* has been augmented with a series of transducing surfaces, loudspeakers, and microphones. Two windows are fitted with both transducers and contact microphones, and a wooden and a metal plate are fitted with two transducers, one contact microphone and a lavalier mic (see Fig.5). In Fig.5, at the top, two hanging objects can be seen, a sound field microphone in the far end and slightly closer an ultrasonic emitter array. A closeup of the emitter can be seen in Fig.6.

The performances during the season were four five-hour improvisations per week where four dancers perform together with one musician who controls a set of composed feedback processes that connect various inputs and outputs in the space via custom signal processing software. As the room, and often several surfaces in the room, become integrated in the feedback systems, the actions and vocalisations of the dancers might have a direct influence on the resulting sounds. However, as the performances are both durational and structured improvisations, with at times four dancers on stage at the same time, some other process through which to link the movements of the dancers to the control of the feedback systems was needed. For this, we attempted to scale up the ultrasound motion estimation to a room-scale capture volume. For this purpose, the multi-emitter pictured in Fig.6 was constructed. As described in Section 4.1, a single regular broadband microphone was used to receive the ultrasound. This was a result of testing combinations of 1) many emitters and a single receiver, 2) one emitter and several receivers, and 3) many pairs of single emitters and single receivers, in several larger rooms. The first options seemed to perform best and that was therefore what was used in *Der Betrieb*. The results of using the multi-emitter and the full-range microphone mounted directly above the emitter were a capture volume of varying quality of about 10 by 5 meters, covering almost the whole floor and extending vertically well above what any of the dancers could reach. In general the

Figure 6. The multi-emitter construction used in The Season of Sound.

strength of the representation of a given movement in the signal at the microphone lessens the further away from the emitter-microphone position at which the movement happens, but movements up to five meters from the center of the room (and even longer actual distance to the emitter-microphone pair as they are several meters above the floor) are perfectly detectable if the movement is unobstructed from the perspective of the emitter-microphone pair. Even more extraordinary is that while the amplitude of the motion estimation diminished towards the edges of the capture volume, the spatial resolution didn't, meaning that even at ten meters apart, two dancers could control feedback systems playing in the room with gestures as small as flicking a finger a centimetre or two, using the single emitter-microphone pair in the middle of the room.

This spatial sensitivity actually led to unexpected new feedback loops forming. While the vibrations in the glass panes were too small to be detected by the ultrasound, the hanging wooden plate sometimes could, and the huge thin metal plate could quite easily create a large impact on the movement estimation. In certain situations, depending on how the mapping between the motion estimation and feedback systems was setup, a positive feedback loop could be unintentionally created where more movement would vibrate the metal plate with a higher amplitude, leading to more movement being detected, and so on.

Der Betrieb is an open performance space, meaning that the audience is free to enter and leave whenever they like during the opening hours, and furthermore are free to move

around the space and sit wherever they like. As the ultrasonic motion estimation isn't depending on tracking anything particular (e.g. a ball reflective in the infra red spectrum, or an object with a certain color or a fiducial marker), the movement of the audience members is as influential as that of the dancers. This heightened charge in the space, when identified by the audience can lead to surprising and artistically fertile situations that deserve deeper exploration.

These findings suggest significant potential and a wealth of unexplored opportunities for research and artistic exploration using ultrasonic motion estimation in room-scale environments - and potentially beyond.

6. DISCUSSION

The three case study pieces offer quite different types of application of the ultrasound motion estimation technique.

In *Autotrope n.4*, the ultrasound is linked to an object rather than a performer. The performer's movements are always understood as in relation to the metal plate, and even when the performer isn't directly touching the plate, the ultrasound is still sensing the movements of the plate resulting from the vibrations induced by the transducer. The two cases are made distinct in their interpretation of the control signals derived from the ultrasound motion estimation. When directly manipulated, the signal is filtered such that only big changes are detected and used as triggers to change the signal processing abruptly, and while left to itself, the system uses the motion estimation directly as a modulation signal. Still, the system is tuned such that the interaction and feedback processes concern the behaviours of the plate, rather than the performer interacting with it.

In *Speculator*, the ultrasound sensing is also mounted on an instrument. While the double bass in itself is much larger than the metal plate mentioned above, the ultrasound transducers are mounted at a similar distance. However, in contrast, the system is tuned to react to very small movements happening in a volume that far extends the space between the transducers, but rather incorporates the whole instrument and a sizeable volume around it. Here, it is clearly the performer that is sensed, not the instrument, allowing for full-body gestures in direct proximity but not necessarily directly between the transducers.

In *The Season of Sound*, the motion estimation moves beyond the single performer and opens up a room-scale volume inhabited by both performers and audience members. This is made possible by the fact that the decrease in quality as one moves away from the sensed area is one of magnitude, not resolution. In camera-based motion capture, being further away from the camera means that a movement is covered by a more coarse resolution as it becomes smaller from the perspective of the camera. This is not strictly the case for the ultrasound motion estimation. Moving away from the transducers means that there are fewer rays of ultrasound to interact with, which could lessen the resolution somewhat, but it primarily affects the magnitude of the detected change, i.e. if you are *seen* by the system, the same movement qualities can be detected, they will just have a more faint effect. This means that the

edges of the detection volume are not clear, rather, there is a tapering off of the motion's influence when moving further and further away from the transducers. This has two important consequences. Firstly, it allows a system to define its boundaries by choosing its sensitivity such that only that which should influence it actually is. An infinite capture volume, while impressive, would not always be practical. Secondly, it allows a performer to temper their influence on the system they are interacting with by positioning themselves accordingly. This can involve everything from theremin-like gestures to moving several meters to another part of a room, as we have seen in the case studies.

Shadowing is another way in which the motion estimation is modulated spatially. This was a prominent feature of the system set up in *Der Betrieb*, where the dancers could play with their relative positioning with regards to the centrally placed transducers hanging from the ceiling. At a distance beyond a few meters radially from the center of the room, the ultrasound rays were filling the space such that a dancer cast a shadow outward from the perspective of the transducers. This shadow from an inner dancer could occlude the movements of an outer dancer, further away from the middle of the room. This kind of co-constructed dynamic terrain allows for several ways of navigating the varying intensities of movement consequences throughout a space. The dancers also quickly found strategies of self-occlusion to modulate the impact of their movements by finding ways of hiding or showing a gesture to different degrees, e.g. using their body to envelope a hand gesture or moving an arm behind their back while standing close to a wall facing the room, and then gradually or suddenly revealing the gestures to control the resulting effects. These explorations show how visceral, embodied and spatial the ultrasound material became and we again highly encourage further exploration in these kinds of large-volume situations.

In addition to differences in what is sensed and the scale of the volume in which it is sensed, the three pieces also apply the result of the sensing with different intentions. *Autotrope n.4* shows how working with thresholds can produce discreet events that in turn can trigger clearly defined state changes in a system. *Speculator* uses continuous modulation of a complex system, intertwining intention and serendipity by charging the actions of playing the double bass with a double meaning. *The Season of Sound* unfolds the complexity even further by having several performers and audience members navigating a space that they are also involved in creating.

All in all, the variety in the three applications of motion estimation shows the strength of the approach, as it supports a wide gamut of contexts and goals.

7. SUMMARY

This article proposed an approach to motion estimation for musical applications using ultrasonic technology and low-cost, off-the-shelf components, through a general technical description of the setup and three practical application examples. A variety of implementations has been discussed, both in the construction of different types of emitters and in

the choice of the receivers, ranging from specialised ultrasonic transducers to general microphones capable of operating at the desired frequency. The variety of applications and implementations demonstrates the versatility of the proposed approach that, combined with the low cost of its components, makes it a very accessible system for motion estimation in musical applications. Compared to high-fidelity motion capture technologies, the trade-off between expenses, portability, calibration and installation complexity, proved the proposed ultrasound-based system to be very worthwhile to explore, especially in musical contexts requiring a plug-and-play setup.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] L. Elblaus, Å. Unander-Scharin, and C. Unander-Scharin, “New scenic subjects: explorations of a system of autonomous on-stage observers,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2016, pp. 265–268.
- [2] E. Frid, R. Bresin, P. Alborn, and L. Elblaus, “Interactive sonification of spontaneous movement of children—cross-modal mapping and the perception of body movement qualities through sound,” *Frontiers in neuroscience*, vol. 10, p. 521, 2016.
- [3] T. Bovermann, J. Groten, A. deCampo, and G. Eckel, “Juggling sounds,” in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Interactive Sonification*, 2007.
- [4] G. Eckel, D. Pirrò, and G. Sharma, “Motion-enabled live electronics,” in *Proceedings of the 6th Sound and Music Computing Conference, Porto, Portugal*, 2009.
- [5] K. Groß-Vogt, D. Pirrò, I. Kobenz, R. Höldrich, and G. Eckel, “Physiosonic - evaluated movement sonification as auditory feedback in physiotherapy,” in *International Symposium on Computer Music Modeling and Retrieval*, 01 2009, pp. 103–120.
- [6] M. Yoneyama, J.-i. Fujimoto, Y. Kawamo, and S. Sasabe, “The audio spotlight: An application of non-linear interaction of sound waves to a new type of loudspeaker design,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 73, no. 5, pp. 1532–1536, 1983.
- [7] J. Pampin, J. Kollin, and E. Kang, “Applications of Ultrasonic Sound Beams in Performance and Sound Art,” in *International Computer Music Conference*, 2007.
- [8] M. Alunno, “Sound Straight Ahead: Parametric Speakers in Two Soundscape Installations,” *Leonardo Music Journal*, vol. 28, pp. 60–64, 2018.
- [9] T. Sadowsky, Ed., *Teasing Chaos. David Tudor*. Museum der Moderne Salzburg: Kehrer Verlag, 2021.
- [10] D. Overholt, “The Overtone Violin,” in *New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, Vancouver, 2005.
- [11] M. Ciglar, “An Ultrasound Based Instrument Generating Audible and Tactile Sound,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, 2010, pp. 19–22.
- [12] G.-W. Raes, “Gesture Controlled Musical Instruments - Godfried-Willem Raes,” <https://logosfoundation.org/ii/gesture-instrument.html>, 2011.
- [13] D. Pozzi, “Ron Kuivila’s Open Air Synthesizer in “Listening To The Air”,” <https://www.researchcatalogue.net/view/386118/432464>, 2018.
- [14] N. Robson, A. McPherson, and N. Bryan-Kinns, “Being With The Waves: An Ultrasonic Art Installation Enabling Rich Interaction Without Sensors,” in *International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, 2022.
- [15] G. Eckel, “Speculator,” in *Proceedings of the Speculative Sound Synthesis Symposium*, 2024.